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Research Article

To Enhancement Of The Antifungal Activity Of Hydroalcoholic Leaf Extract Of Euphorbia Hirta By Utilizing Silver Nanoparticles Gel

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ABSTRACT

Background:

The biggest organ in a person's body, skin forms a barrier to protect internal organs from the outside environment. In this disease develop & evolution of fungal infection play a major role ROS, cell death. Euphorbia hirta is capable to protect and kill microbes its work as antifungal or anti-bacterial. The current investigation aimed to examine the enhance the antifungal effect of euphorbia hirta extract combination and formulate with silver nanoparticle gel against the fungal infection.

Method:

Synthesizing nanoparticles through physical, chemical, and biological approaches, and formulating silver nanoparticle gel. E. hirta's properties were examined & comparison with standard drug fluconazole. Through relaxation impact, depressive effects, and medicinal uses solubility studies, FTIR analysis, partition coefficient determination, evaluation of silver nanoparticles, UV spectroscopy, particle size analysis, drug entrapment efficiency determination, transmission electron microscopy, zeta potential analysis, and formulation of silver nanoparticle gel.

Result

The study demonstrated improved drug penetration and reduced side effects with nanoparticle-sized particles. Silver nanoparticle gel showed potent antifungal properties and controlled release benefits. E. hirta showed anti-asthmatic properties and various medicinal uses. Silver nanoparticles gel of E. hirta exhibited antifungal activity against a range of different fungus *Candida albicans*, *Aspergillus niger*, *Trichophyton rubrum* or reduced toxicity. Controlled drug release kinetics observed in the gel formulation of E. hirta.

Conclusion:

SNG2 had the highest efficacy and antifungal activity. SNG2 released the drug more effectively than SNG1 and SNG3. Silver nanoparticles showed potent antifungal and

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antibacterial properties. SNG2 exhibited successful treatment of fungal infections and acne.

INTRODUCTION

Fungal infections, also known as mycoses, are diseases caused by fungi. These infections can affect various parts of the body, including the skin, nails, lungs, and internal organs. Fungi are a diverse group of organisms that include yeasts, Molds, and mushrooms. While many fungi are harmless and live in the environment, some can cause infections, particularly in individuals with weakened immune systems.[1]

Pathophysiology of fungal infection

Fungal infections, or mycoses, exhibit a wide range of pathophysiological mechanisms that depend on the type of fungus, the site of infection, and the host's immune status. The pathophysiology involves a complex interplay of fungal virulence factors and host immune responses. This note provides an in-depth overview of the pathophysiological processes involved in fungal infections.[2]

Nanotechnology:

Utilizing nanotechnology, a novel therapeutic approach for medication enhancement has been created. By creating nanoparticles and taking use of their optoelectronic and physicochemical characteristics, nanotechnology has become a new tool in the fight against deadly microbial diseases. Conventional antimicrobials have limitations that can be addressed by nanoparticle-based methods. Nanoparticles are used to target microbial diseases as nano-drugs and nano-cargo.[3] Nanotechnology has applications in the areas of waste-free production, sunscreens, antibacterial sanitizers, drug delivery, and diagnostic procedures. The development of environmentally friendly nanotechnology has piqued the attention of researchers in the biogenesis of green nanoparticles. Broad-spectrum antibacterial properties against both Gram-positive and Gram-

negative bacterial strains, as well as antifungal activity against a variety of fungus strains, have been documented for nanoparticles. metallic nanoparticles in a variety of forms figure 1.8, such as Au-based, Mg-based, Ag-based, ZnO, Fe₃O₄, NO, and CuO NPs.[4]

Formulation of silver nanoparticle gel & benefit:

AgNPs are created in a gel matrix via a multi-step process that includes the synthesis of a silver precursor, reduction to create nanoparticles, and stabilization in a polymer gel. To start, distilled water is used to dissolve silver nitrate (AgNO₃) and produce a silver precursor solution. The reduction of silver ions to nanoparticles is then facilitated by adding a reducing agent, such as sodium borohydride (NaBH₃), dropwise to the silver nitrate solution while stirring continuously. A color shift, usually to brown or yellow, denotes the reduction process and the creation of AgNPs. Simultaneously, a polymer such as polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) is dissolved in water by heating and agitating it until it dissolves completely, creating a gel matrix. To guarantee even dispersion, the cooled colloidal AgNP solution is combined with the gel matrix while being constantly stirred. After that, this mixture is left to gel at room temperature, producing a stable AgNPs gel.[5] There are several advantages to adding silver nanoparticles to a gel matrix, especially when it comes to medicinal and environmental uses. The silver nanoparticles'-controlled release method in gel form maximizes their antibacterial qualities while reducing any possible harm. AgNPs gels are therefore very useful as wound dressings since they may discharge silver ions continually, preventing infections and accelerating healing. Furthermore, the gel matrix keeps the nanoparticles stable, avoiding agglomeration and preserving their effectiveness for longer periods of time.[6]

Due to its capacity to absorb and neutralize pollutants over time, its stability is useful in ecological uses like filtering water. All things considered, polymers gels' versatility & stability properties mix has the strong antibacterial properties of AgNPs to generate nanoparticle-like silver gels, a multipurpose material with an array of uses.[7]

Euphorbia hirta:

The three indigenous medical systems—Ayurvedic, Siddha, and Unani—have been practiced for many millennia. Certain Ayurvedic medications that treat contemporary illnesses are currently available on the market figure 1.17 Even though synthetic medications are useful in treating a variety of illnesses, millions of individuals cannot afford them. Roughly 70,000 plant species are thought to have been utilized medicinally. The basic ingredient needed to synthesize conventional medications is found in the plants. Medicinal plants' diverse chemical components provide them their therapeutic properties. More than 2500 plant species are known to have medicinal benefit in India; over 1400 are recognized in Sri Lanka; and roughly 700 in Nepal.[8]. This plant has several therapeutic activities like, antibacterial, antifungal,

antimalarial, anti-inflammatory, and good property as antioxidant [9]

MATERIAL & METHOD:

Authentication of Plant: Euphorbia hirta leaves were gathered for verification and delivered to the Akal College of Pharmacy & Technical Education in Gursagar, Mastana Sahib, Sangrur, Punjab..[10]
Drug-Loaded Silver Nanoparticle

Preparation of Drug-Loaded Silver Nanoparticle:

In order to create a 1 mM concentration of silver nanoparticles, several dosages of the medication quercetin dihydrate (10 mg, 20 mg, 30 mg, 40 mg, and 50 mg) were introduced into distinct growth tubes. Ten millilitres of the silver nanoparticle solution were added to each culture tube. All culture tube's contents were well combined. The combined solutions underwent a 15-minute centrifugation at 5000 pm. After centrifugation, the supernatant was collected leaving behind any sediment or precipitate. The collected supernatant which includes silver nanoparticles, was subsequently studied and used for different application the: Composition of Different Quercetin dihydrate silver Nanoparticles is presented in Table No. 1.1 [11]

Table No. 1 Preparation of Drug-Loaded Silver Nanoparticle

Code	Drug amount (mg)	Nanoparticle solution volume (ml)
F2A5	50	2
F2A4	40	2
F2A3	30	2
F2A2	20	2
F2A1	10	2

Characterisation of Quercetin dihydrate loaded silver nanoparticle

Percentage yield:

In order to create a 1 mM concentration of silver nanoparticles, several dosages of the medication quercetin dihydrate (10 mg, 20 mg, 30 mg, 40 mg, and 50 mg) were introduced into distinct growth

tubes. Ten millilitres (millilitres) of the silver nanoparticle solution were added to each culture tube. All of the ingredients in each culture tube were well combined. For fifteen minutes, at 5000 pm, the combined solutions were centrifuged. The supernatant—which included any sediment or precipitate—was collected following

centrifugation. Table No. 1.1 displays the composition of different quercetin dihydrate silver nanoparticles. The collected supernatant,

containing silver nanoparticles, was subsequently investigated & employed for various applications [12]

$$\text{Percentage yield} = \frac{\text{Partical mass of nanoparticle (final weight)}}{\text{Theoretical mass (Excipient + drug)}} \times 1$$

Drug Entrapment Efficiency:

The following procedures typically occur to try determine an amount of quercetin dihydrate entrapped in silver nanoparticles using a centrifugation method. First, make the silver nanoparticles containing quercetin dihydrate. In order to separate the nanoparticles into the supernatant, the created silver nanoparticle solution was centrifuged thereafter. gathered the

supernatant and centrifuged it one more using water. Reduce the sample's concentration. diluted a supernatant sample using the proper technique, such HPLC. The total absorbance of the sample was determined by comparing the absorbance of the supernatant Quercetin dihydrate free silver nanoparticle.[13]. This formula was used to compute the percentage entrapment efficiency Equation No. 2:

$$\% \text{Entrapment Efficiency} = \frac{\text{Added drug} - \text{free drug}}{\text{Amount of drug added}} \times 100 \dots (\text{equation 2})$$

Particle size:

The pride it of the quercetin size distribution parties was ascertained by means of the Dynamic Light Scattering (LS) approach. Measuring the size distribution of particles in a liquid solution is a potent analytical approach. LS gathers data on particle size and size distribution by tracking variations in light scattering intensity brought on by the Brownian motion of particles. A laser beam is sent through the suspension of a sample when it is being exposed to DS analysis, and the scattered light is then detected and examined. (Bhat et al., 2019).

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM):

The quercetin-loaded silver nanoparticles were characterized using Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM). Ag-NPs, or silver nanoparticles, may be effectively characterized using this potent approach. With the use of TEM's high-resolution imaging capabilities, each nanoparticle morphology, size, and shape may be seen and studied. A tiny quantity of the colloidal

solution that was created to contain the nanoparticles was usually applied to a thin copper grid that had been covered in a polymer film in order to conduct a transmission electron microscopy (TEM) study of silver nanoparticles. The resultant TEM picture offers comprehensive details on the nanoparticles' size, shape, and arrangement. TEM makes it possible to observe individual nanoparticles with extremely high resolution, frequently at the nano-meter scale. (Tasca et al., 2020).

FTIR.

A chemical or medicine's FT-IR (Fourier Transform Infrared) spectra can show which groups are present. FTIR spectroscopy was used for structural study in order to look for any possible drug interactions with excipients. an FTIR spectra of a combination of dihydrate quercetin silver nanoparticles loaded with other substances were noted. FT-IR chamber was supplied with 1-2 mg Regarding quercetin dihydrate loaded nanoparticle of silver. The

infrared spectrum's range of 4000 to 400 cm^{-1} was noticed. (Nagar et al, 2016).

Zeta Potential:

One of the most important factors in determining the stability of nanoparticles in a solution is their zeta potential, which is a measurement of their net surface charge. It offers details on the electrostatic attraction or repulsion that exists between nanoparticles and how it affects the way those particles aggregate or disperse. Electrophoretic mobility is typically utilized to evaluate the Zeta potential of nanoparticle. This technique involved applying an electric field to a suspension of nanoparticles and monitoring the particles' motion as a result of the electric field. The surface charge of the nanoparticles is shown by the zeta potential values, which can be positive or negative. Strong electrostatic repulsion between the particles is indicated when the zeta potential is high (above +30 mV or below -30 mV), which aids in preventing the particles from aggregating. On the other hand, weak electrostatic repulsion, which can cause particle aggregation & instability, is indicated by a low absolute value of the zeta

potential, i.e., one that is near zero. (Bhat et d, 2019).[14]

Preparation of Quercetin dihydrate loaded silver nanoparticle gel:

Quercetin dihydrate entrapped silver nanoparticle gel was prepared using the quasi-emulsion solvent technique. Quercetin dihydrate loaded silver nanoparticles, silver nitrate solution (1% or 2%), Carbopol 934 (2%), and triethanolamine (sufficient quantity) were incorporated in the gel base composition. A detailed method for creating the gel is provided below: created the silver nanoparticle solution loaded with quercetin dihydrate by utilizing the appropriate concentration of silver nitrate solution. Once the carbopol dispersion was homogenized, gradually add the solution of silver nanoparticles loaded with quercetin dihydrate while stirring constantly. After thoroughly mixing, put the gel into appropriate tubes or containers for storage and future use. The composition of several quercetin dihydrate-loaded silver nanoparticle gels is listed in Table No. 1.2 [15]

.Table 2 Composition of different quercetin dihydrate loaded silver nanoparticle gel

Sr. no.	Ingredients	Formulation code	
		F2A5B7	F2A5B6
1	Triethanolamine (ml)	Q. S	Q. S
2	Carbopol 934 (% w/v)	2	1
3	Quercetin dihydrate (mg)	20	20
4	Quercetin dihydrate loaded silver nanoparticle gel (ml)	2	2

Evaluation of Quercetin dihydrate loaded silver nanoparticle gels

Visual Appearance:

The freshly formed gels were examined visually, and the resulting formulations' physical characteristics (such as color and homogeneity) were carefully examined. (Nadia et al., 2013).

pH determination:

A digital pH scale was utilized to measure the pH of the quercetin dihydrate loaded silver nanogel formulations. The steps that were taken are as follows: dissolved one gram of the gel mixture in 100 millilitres of purified water. made sure to thoroughly mix in order to have a uniform solution. calibrated the digital pH meter using common HI buffer solutions to get it ready. made

sure the pH meter's electrodes was making great contact with the gel by submerging it in the gel solution. (Nagaich et al., 2016).

Viscosity:

The viscosity of the sample was measured for rheological investigations using a viscometer. The steps that were taken are as follows: 20 grams of the sample should be taken and put in a beaker. Give the sample five minutes to adjust before entering the room temperature and return to normal. The viscometer was configured using a T-4 spindle, which was started at five revolutions per minute. The spindle was then dropped into the sample, making sure it was completely submerged, and the viscometer was left to run for a long enough period of time to guarantee consistent readings on the dial. The average viscosity value is calculated by summing the two readings and dividing by two by following this technique and taking the test at a regulated speed or temperature. This reveals the viscosity of the sample. The measurement was conducted twice to verify uniformity. It offers important details on the formulation's viscosity for quercetin dihydrate-loaded silver nanogel.

Spreadability Study:

In this study, the gel's spreadability was evaluated using a lab-built instrument built of two glass slides. A certain weight was added to the upper slide during the operation, and the displacement of the top slide was monitored. The amount of time it took for the top slide to move out of position was noted. The gel's spreadability (S) was computed using Equation No. 6:

$$S = m * \frac{1}{t} \dots \dots \dots (Equation 6)$$

Where: 'S' stands for the gel's spreadability. 'm' stands for the weight fastened to the upper slide. 'T' stands for the glass slide's length. [15]. (Nagaich et al., 2016).

In vitro release studies:

In the in vitro release investigations, Franz diffusion cells were utilized. These cells consisted of a donor compartment and a receptor compartment, which were separated by a cellophane membrane. The cellophane membrane top surface was in contact with the drug formulation solution, while the receptor compartment contained phosphate buffer at pH 7.4. The effective sectional area of the diffusion cell was 3.14cm² recived chamber, & a capacity of 15 ml the cellophane membrane was securely fastened to ensure a proper barrier between the donor and receptor compartment the entire assembly was placed on Using a magnetic bead and stirrer, the fluid in the receptor chamber was continually mixed. To maintain sink conditions and guarantee a consistent volume, an equivalent volume of new dissolving medium (phosphate buffer, pH 7.4) was put back to the receptor compartment after each sampling. The in vitro release profile of quercetin dihydrate from the gel formulation during a given time period may be examined thanks to this arrangement. (Jangde et al., 2018).

Drug release kinetic studies

Different kinetic models were used in the study of the in vitro release data to ascertain the release kinetics and percent drug release of the improved formulation from floating beads. The models utilized were the Korsmeyer-Peppas Equation, the Zero-order Equation, the First-order Equation, and Higuchi's Model. It is possible to calculate the % drug release and release kinetics of the optimal formulation from floating beads by fitting the experimental data to these kinetic models. Every model sheds light on the release process and may be used to assess how well a formulation performs in terms of its ability to release substances gradually or instantly. (Sharma et.al, 2021).

Results: Ash value: total ash value of *Euphorbia hirta* linn is $9.71 + 0.04$, & acid soluble value obtained is $1.40 + 0.36$

Extraction process:

The plant material, typically the aerial parts, is collected and thoroughly washed to remove any dirt and impurities. After cleaning, the plant material is dried, either under shade or in a drying oven at a controlled temperature to prevent the degradation of its active constituents. Once dried, the material is finely powdered to increase the surface area for the extraction process. The powdered plant material is then subjected to maceration or percolation using a hydroalcoholic solvent, which is a mixture of water and ethanol. The ratio of ethanol to water can vary, but a common mixture is 70% ethanol and 30% water. This solvent system is chosen because it is effective in extracting both polar and non-polar compounds present in the plant. The maceration process typically lasts for several days, with occasional stirring to ensure thorough mixing and better extraction efficiency. After the extraction period, the solvent containing the dissolved active compounds is separated from the plant residue by filtration. The filtrate is then concentrated under reduced pressure using a rotary evaporator to remove the ethanol, leaving behind a thick, concentrated extract. This extract can be further dried, if necessary, using a freeze-dryer or a vacuum oven to obtain a dry powder. The final hydroalcoholic extract of *Euphorbia hirta* Linn is then stored in airtight containers

Isolation of the drug (Quercetin):

Silica gel and ethyl acetate were used as the stationary and mobile phases in column chromatography, which was used to isolate quercetin. 29 fractions total were collected, with a volume of 4.0 ml.

Identification by TLC:

Chromatography using thin layers the produced TLC plates displayed spots that matched the reference quercetin and ethanol extract of *Euphorbia hirta* when they got saturated with iodine vapours (Fig. 4.1 A). The results of the ethanol extraction of *Euphorbia hirta* from the plates produced under ultraviolet (UV) are shown in (B). Additionally, the concentrated test sample's thin layer chromatogram.

(A)

(B)

(C)

Figure 1 A) Thin layer chromatogram of ethanol extract of Euphorbia hirta B) Thin layer

chromatogram of ethanol extract of Euphorbia hirta UV trans illuminator C) TLC of concentrated quercetin of Euphorbia hirta under UV trans illuminator

Calibration Curve of Quercetin dihydrate:

Utilizing the 10µg/ml to 50µg/ml solution, a calibration curves for µg/ml was produced. Regression equation $Y=81992x - 28533$ and R2 value 0.999 are represented by a calibration curve in the graph, and Figure 3 illustrates this strong linearity.

Figure 2 Calibration curve of Drug Quercetin dihydrate Quercetin dihydrate-loaded silver nanoparticles (F2A1-F2A5)

Sr. No.	Formulation Code	% Yield
1	F2A1	86.12±1.155
2	F2A2	90.54±1.091
3	F2A3	93.10±0.371
4	F2A4	92.86±1.748
5	F2A5	95.64±0.539

Drug Entrapment Efficiency

The drug entrapment effectiveness of silver nanoparticles loaded with quercetin dihydrate varies between 76.70±0.13 and 89.18±0.19. The

maximal drug entrapment for formulation F2A5 is 89.18±0.19.

Particle size:

Results			
Hydrodynamic diameter	195.59 nm	Mean Intensity	288.6 counts/s
Polydispersity Index	33.3 %	Absolute Intensity	142251.5 counts/s
Diffusion coefficient	0.6 $\mu\text{m}^2/\text{s}$	Intercept g^1	0.7248
Transmittance	0.1 %	Baseline	1.038

Figure 3 Particle size of F2A5 formulation

The silver nanoparticle loaded with quercetin dihydrate had a hydrodynamic diameter of 95.59 nm and a polydispersity index of 33.3%

Figure 4 Quercetin dihydrate-loaded silver nanoparticle analysis using FTIR

the FTIR spectra of Euphorbia hirta silver nanoparticles loaded with quercetin dihydrate. The O-H stretch peak is located at 3338.22 cm^{-1} , whereas the C=C stretch peak is located at 1635.22 cm^{-1} . Silver ions and other functional groups on

the edge of quercetin dihydrate interact through the creation of coordination bonds, as seen by the fluctuation of peaks in Figure 4.20.

Zeta Potential

Figure 5 Quercetin dihydrate-loaded silver nanoparticle

The silver nanoparticles coated with quercetin dihydrate by the formulation F2A5's zeta potential of -15.3 mV. The silver nanoparticles coated with quercetin dihydrate have a stable formulation, as indicated mV.

In Vitro Drug Release Studies:

Sr. No.	Time (Hr)	Drug Release of Pure Drug	Drug Release of Formulation F2A5B6	Drug Release of Formulation F2A5B7
1	0	0	0	0
2	0.5	18.605±0.142	4.473±0.027	3.985±0.072
3	1	39.984±0.086	9.949±0.068	9.166±0.714
4	2	59.769±0.511	20.648±0.013	16.518±2.811
5	4	66.062±0.254	35.376±0.511	31.454±3.038
6	6	85.291±0.975	53.294±2.668	46.438±1.565
7	8	95.273±0.251	74.575±0.076	70.007±1.032
8	12		88.868±2.985	85.326±2.260
9	24		97.745±0.543	91.607±0.786

Figure 6 Drug release percentage of Quercetin dihydrate-loaded silver nanoparticle gel

Drug release kinetic study
Zero order kinetics

As seen in Figure 1.7, zero- order kinetics of composition F2A5B6 were plotted to study ongoing release of drug.

Figure 7 Zero-order graph

First-order kinetics:

To examine the system's release, the first-order kinetics formulation F2A5B6 was plotted, as seen in Figure 1.8.

Figure 8 First order

Higuchi's model:

The drug release from the matrix is seen in Figure 1.9 and is modelled using Higuchi's formulation F2A5B6.

Figure 9 Higuchi's model

Korsmeyer-Peppas Model:

Figure 10 Korsmeyer-Peppas

Kinetic equation parameter of F2A5B6 Formulation:

Table no 5 F2A5B6 formulation

Formulation Code	Zero-order		First-order		Higuchi		K. Peppas	
	K ₀	R ²						
F6	4.105	0.803	-0.072	0.987	25.077	0.936	0.843	0.788

Anti- fungal activity of optimized silver nanoparticles gel (SNG2):

Antimicrobial activity of the prepared silver nanoparticle gel (SNG2) was assessed.

Table. 6 Anti-fungal activity of standard drug against selected fungus:

Drug	Fungus	Zone of inhibition		
		30 µg/ml	20 µg/ml	10 µg/ml
fluconazole	Candida albicans	17±0.19	15±0.13	12±0.15
nystatin	Aspergillus niger	28±0.5	21±0.57	16±0.86
econazole	Trichophyton rubrum	22±0.5	18±0.57	13±0.86

Table 7Anti-fungal activity prepared silver nanoparticles gel (SNG2)

Sr. no.	Fungus	Zone of inhibition		
		Ethanolic extract		
		100mg/ml	50 mg/ml	25mg/ml
1.	Candida albicans	15±0.25	13±0.30	11±0.29
2.	Aspergillus niger	17±0.36	15±0.41	12±0.35
3.	Trichophyton rubrum	17±0.32	13±0.35	12±0.24

A) **Candida albicans** B) **Aspergillus niger** C) **Trichophyton rubrum**

Figure 11. A,B,C are Anti- Fungal activity of standard drug, a. fluconazole, b. nystatin and c. econazole on **Candida albicans, Aspergillus niger, Trichophyton rubrum.**

A) **Candida albicans** B) **Aspergillus niger** C) **Trichophyton rubrum**

Figure 12 A, B, C are Anti- Fungal activity of Silver Nanoparticles gel, a. fluconazole, b. nystatin and c. econazole on **Candida albicans, Aspergillus niger, Trichophyton rubrum**

CONCLUSION

Agar plates injected with different fungus were utilized to investigate the antifungal activity of prepared silver nanoparticle gel (SNG2); this is a widely used technique that has been documented previously; the findings. Using agar plates, *Euphorbia hirta* extract was also examined for antifungal activity; it again exhibits an antifungal impact the antifungal effect of silver was enhanced by the creation of silver nanoparticles gel. Antifungal effect of the sample is checked against *Candida albicans*, *Aspergillus niger*, *Trichophyton rubrum* of the culture into sterile nutritional broth and incubated for 24 hours at 37 °C to investigate the antifungal activity of *Euphorbia hirta* extract and create silver nanoparticle gel (SNG2). In antibiogram investigations for both *Euphorbia hirta* extract and silver nanoparticle gel (SNG2), three concentrations of solution—25, 50, and 100 mg/ml—were used to create gel. After 24 hours, plates were checked for distinct zones of inhibition close to the wells impregnated with particular concentrations of medication. The diameter of each wall's zone of inhibition was measured, and the results showed that gel made from silver nanoparticles (SNG2) had potent antibacterial properties. The gel can be used to treat acne since it proved successful in killing the fungal infection

REFERENCES

1. A. Homei and M. Worboys, *Fungal disease in Britain and the United States 1850–2000: Mycoses and modernity*. Springer Nature, 2013.
2. D. M. Dixon and T. J. Walsh, “Antifungal agents,” *Med. Microbiol.* 4th Ed., 1996.
3. A. A. Yetisgin, S. Cetinel, M. Zuvin, A. Kosar, and O. Kutlu, “Therapeutic nanoparticles and their targeted delivery applications,” *Molecules*, vol. 25, no. 9, p. 2193, 2020.
4. B. Bhardwaj, P. Singh, A. Kumar, S. Kumar, and V. Budhwar, “Eco-friendly greener synthesis of nanoparticles,” *Adv. Pharm. Bull.*, vol. 10, no. 4, p. 566, 2020.
5. A. A. H. Abdellatif, H. N. H. Alturki, and H. M. Tawfeek, “Different cellulosic polymers for synthesizing silver nanoparticles with antioxidant and antibacterial activities,” *Sci. Rep.*, vol. 11, no. 1, p. 84, 2021.
6. G. Sabarees, V. Velmurugan, G. P. Tamilarasi, V. Alagarsamy, and V. Raja Solomon, “Recent advances in silver nanoparticles containing nanofibers for chronic wound management,” *Polymers (Basel)*, vol. 14, no. 19, p. 3994, 2022.
7. G. Palani et al., “Silver nanoparticles for waste water management,” *Molecules*, vol. 28, no. 8, p. 3520, 2023.
8. S. Sen, R. Chakraborty, B. De, S. Sen, R. Chakraborty, and B. De, “Indian traditional medicinal systems, herbal medicine, and diabetes,” *Diabetes Mellit. 21st Century*, pp. 125–151, 2016.
9. E. M. Abubakar, “Antibacterial activity of crude extracts of *Euphorbia hirta* against some bacteria associated with enteric infections,” *J. Med. Plants Res.*, vol. 3, no. 7, pp. 498–505, 2009.
10. A. M. Knab et al., “Influence of quercetin supplementation on disease risk factors in community-dwelling adults,” *J. Am. Diet. Assoc.*, vol. 111, no. 4, pp. 542–549, 2011.
11. M. Todorova et al., “Drug-loaded silver nanoparticles—a tool for delivery of a mebeverine precursor in inflammatory bowel diseases treatment,” *Biomedicines*, vol. 11, no. 6, p. 1593, 2023.
12. S. R. K. Pandian, S. Kunjiappan, V. Ravishankar, and V. Sundarapandian,

- “Synthesis of quercetin-functionalized silver nanoparticles by rapid one-pot approach,” *BioTechnologia*, vol. 102, no. 1, p. 75, 2021.
13. M. S. Dhar et al., “Genomic characterization and epidemiology of an emerging SARS-CoV-2 variant in Delhi, India,” *Science (80-.)*, vol. 374, no. 6570, pp. 995–999, 2021.
14. S. Karmakar, “Particle size distribution and zeta potential based on dynamic light scattering: Techniques to characterize stability and surface charge distribution of charged colloids,” *Recent Trends Mater. Phys. Chem*, vol. 28, pp. 117–159, 2019.
15. R. Badhwar, B. Mangla, Y. R. Neupane, K. Khanna, and H. Popli, “Quercetin loaded silver nanoparticles in hydrogel matrices for diabetic wound healing,” *Nanotechnology*, vol. 32, no. 50, p. 505102, 2021.

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